

DEVELOPMENT OF AN IOT-ENABLED REAL-TIME TEMPERATURE DATA LOGGER FOR LABORATORY-SCALE PYROLYSIS REACTOR APPLICATIONS

***¹A. Akinsade, ²B. A. Iyaomolere, ²O. O. Oluwasegun, ¹A. R. Lasisi**

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa, Nigeria

²Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa, Nigeria

***E-mail:** a.akinsade@oaustech.edu.ng, oredynasty@gmail.com.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17963424>

Keywords:

Temperature monitoring, pyrolysis, Arduino, data acquisition system, embedded system, IoT-enable data logger

Abstract: Precise temperature measurement is essential in pyrolysis processes where thermal gradients strongly affect reaction kinetics, product yield, and process efficiency. This study presents the design, development, and experimental validation of an Internet of Things (IoT) enabled real time temperature data logger for laboratory scale pyrolysis reactor applications. The system integrates four K type MAX6675K thermocouple sensors with an Arduino Nano for data acquisition and an ESP32 microcontroller for wireless data transmission to the ThingSpeak cloud platform. It includes LCD and OLED displays for local visualization, a lithium ion battery with a battery management system for autonomous operation, and a buzzer for temperature threshold alerts. During the experimental procedure, the data logger was interfaced with a laboratory scale pyrolysis reactor and operated continuously for one hour to record temperature variations at the heater, reactor chamber, condenser inlet, and condenser outlet. The system achieved peak readings of 695.5 °C and 350 °C at the heater and reactor, respectively, while maintaining stable condensation temperatures around 30 °C and 29 °C. The results confirm high accuracy, operational stability, and efficient real time data transmission. The developed system provides a cost effective, scalable, and energy efficient solution for continuous temperature monitoring and process optimization in thermochemical research and smart laboratory automation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for real time data monitoring in scientific research and industrial processes has accelerated advancements in

embedded systems and microcontroller technologies. These innovations have enabled the development of portable, cost effective, and efficient Data Acquisition Systems (DAS),

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

particularly for monitoring physical parameters such as temperature, pressure, and humidity (Waghmare and Chatur, 2012; Obi *et al.*, 2020). A DAS integrates hardware and software to collect, process, and store data from physical phenomena for analysis and decision making. Microcontrollers have become the cornerstone of modern DAS applications due to their compactness, low power consumption, affordability, and processing versatility (Sarma *et al.*, 2018; Osinowo *et al.*, 2022). In thermal systems and chemical process research, such as pyrolysis, where temperature is a critical operational variable, the reliability of data logging systems directly influences process optimization, reproducibility, and safety.

Pyrolysis is a thermochemical process that involves the decomposition of organic matter at elevated temperatures, typically between 300 °C and 600 °C, in the absence of oxygen to produce bio oil, char, and syngas (Aboelela *et al.*, 2023; Akinsade *et al.*, 2025). The yield and quality of these products are strongly dependent on accurate temperature control and monitoring within distinct reactor zones. Variations in heating rate or thermal gradients can alter product distribution and conversion efficiency. Therefore, precise multipoint temperature measurement systems are essential for assessing reaction kinetics and ensuring operational stability in laboratory and industrial scale pyrolysis systems (Pedroza *et al.*, 2014; Mogaji *et al.*, 2019). Conventional temperature measurement instruments such as

thermometers and analogue thermocouples often lack the temporal resolution and automation required for modern process monitoring, underscoring the need for intelligent, IoT based data logging systems.

In response to these limitations, several researchers have developed temperature data loggers using microcontroller platforms. Bora and Sarma (2012) designed a low cost USB based DAS with four analogue input channels using a PIC18LF4553 microcontroller, while Ojike *et al.* (2016) implemented a six channel temperature data logger using LM35 sensors and an Arduino Uno board for real time multi point temperature profiling. Similarly, Ojike *et al.* (2016) developed a six-channel temperature data logger using LM35 sensors interfaced with an Arduino Uno board, demonstrating real time temperature profiling across multiple locations. In a related work, Abrar and Patil (2013) designed a multipoint temperature data logger and PC display system using Zigbee and PSoC technology, further underscoring the evolution of embedded wireless DAS architectures for remote monitoring. Microcontroller-based data loggers, particularly those built around Arduino architecture, offer significant advantages, including modularity, scalability, and compatibility with a range of sensors. The incorporation of digital thermocouple interfaces such as the MAX6675 enhances measurement accuracy and extends the operational range up to 1023 °C, making them ideal for high temperature

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

applications like biomass pyrolysis (Ojike *et al.*, 2016; Obi *et al.*, 2020).

The advent of the Internet of Things (IoT) has further transformed data acquisition systems by enabling real time communication and remote accessibility. IoT integration through modules such as the ESP32 allows logged data to be wirelessly transmitted to cloud platforms like ThingSpeak for real time visualization, storage, and analysis (Ojike *et al.*, 2016; Iyaomolere *et al.*, 2025). This capability eliminates manual data retrieval, facilitates continuous monitoring, and supports data driven control in process automation (Zhairy *et al.*, 2025). Despite these advancements, the cost and complexity of commercially available high precision multi-channel temperature logging systems remain prohibitive, particularly in developing countries, thereby limiting access to continuous and reproducible temperature data in research environments.

This study therefore aims to design and develop a low cost, accurate, and portable IoT enabled four channel temperature data logger for real time monitoring of laboratory scale pyrolysis reactors. The system integrates MAX6675K thermocouple sensors, an Arduino Nano for data acquisition, and an ESP32 microcontroller for wireless transmission. By combining affordability, precision, and IoT functionality, the proposed design seeks to bridge the technological gap in temperature monitoring for thermochemical systems, providing a reliable and scalable platform for laboratory research,

process optimization, and educational applications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 System Design Overview

The IoT enabled real time temperature data logger was designed to facilitate continuous, accurate, and remotely accessible temperature monitoring for a laboratory scale pyrolysis reactor. The overall system architecture, illustrated in Figure 1, integrates five major functional units: the sensing unit, amplifier module, microcontroller unit, WiFi module, and display unit, all powered by a dedicated power supply block. Each unit performs a specific role that contributes to the overall functionality of the system; ranging from temperature detection and signal conditioning to data processing, transmission, and visualization. The design emphasizes modularity, reliability, and scalability, ensuring that each subsystem operates in a synchronized manner for efficient data acquisition and cloud based storage.

In the system workflow, the thermocouple sensors form the sensing unit, which detects temperature variations at selected points of the pyrolysis reactor. The analog signals generated by the sensors are transmitted to the amplifier module, which performs signal conditioning by amplifying, filtering, and converting the temperature signals into a digital format interpretable by the microcontroller unit. The microcontroller unit serves as the central control hub, coordinating data acquisition, processing, and communication tasks. It simultaneously

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

updates the display unit to provide onsite visualization of temperature readings during reactor operation. The processed data are then transmitted to the WiFi module, which functions as the IoT communication interface by wirelessly linking the system to a cloud server for remote data storage and monitoring. The cloud server subsequently transfers the data to a web dashboard, allowing real time visualization and analytical assessment from any internet

connected device. The entire setup is powered by a power supply unit that ensures a stable and regulated voltage for all modules. This systematic interaction between the various hardware blocks provides an efficient platform for real time data logging, enhances process control, and supports experimental reproducibility in laboratory scale pyrolysis studies.

Figure 1: System Architecture of the IoT-enabled Temperature Data Logger

2.2 Hardware Components

The hardware configuration of the IoT enabled real time temperature data logger integrates several functional modules that work collaboratively to ensure accurate temperature

measurement, reliable data processing, and effective wireless communication. The system comprises a sensing unit, a signal conditioning unit, a control and processing unit, a communication unit, a display interface, and a

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

power supply unit. Each module was carefully selected based on performance, energy efficiency, availability, and compatibility with the system design. The specifications of the key components are presented in Table 1, while Figure 2 shows the thermocouple sensor employed as the principal temperature sensing device.

A K type thermocouple sensor was utilized as the main temperature sensing element due to its suitability for high temperature measurement and stable operation in harsh thermal environments. This sensor was specifically chosen for its wide measurement range (0 to 1023 °C), high accuracy, and robustness under the rapid temperature fluctuations typical of pyrolysis processes. The K type thermocouple is

composed of chromel and alumel alloys, which offer strong resistance to oxidation and corrosion while maintaining reliable sensitivity and quick response to temperature changes. These characteristics make it ideal for laboratory scale pyrolysis studies, where precise temperature tracking is critical for understanding thermal decomposition dynamics and optimizing reaction parameters. The thermocouple was interfaced with the MAX6675K amplifier module, which performs analog to digital conversion and cold junction compensation, ensuring that the measured temperature signals are free from interference and accurately transmitted to the control unit. The image of the K type thermocouple sensor used in this design is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: K type thermocouple sensor with MAX6675K amplifier module (Prima *et al.*, 2017)

The Arduino Nano (ATmega328P) microcontroller serves as the main control unit responsible for signal acquisition, processing,

and coordination of all connected modules. It was selected because of its compactness, low power consumption, and capacity to handle multiple sensor inputs simultaneously. The ESP32 microcontroller functions as the communication interface, providing WiFi

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

connectivity for uploading temperature data to the ThingSpeak cloud platform where they can be visualized and analyzed remotely (Iyaomolere *et al.*, 2025). Local monitoring is achieved through the integration of a 2004 Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) and a 1306 Organic Light Emitting Diode (OLED) display, both connected via the I²C interface to enable real time visualization of temperature readings during experiments. The entire system is powered by a lithium 18650 rechargeable battery with an integrated battery management system (BMS) to prevent overcharging and ensure safety during

operation. A DC to DC MP1584 buck converter regulates the voltage supply, maintaining a consistent 5 V DC output to support stable performance across all components. Supplementary elements, including a potentiometer, DC switch, and wiring connections, provide operational control, circuit protection, and efficient power distribution. The deliberate selection and integration of these components ensure the reliability, accuracy, and efficiency of the data logger, making it well suited for continuous temperature monitoring in laboratory scale pyrolysis experiments.

Table 1: Specification of major components used in the system design

Component	Model / Type	Function	Key Specifications	Justification for Selection
Temperature Sensor	K-Type Thermocouple with MAX6675K Module	Measures reactor temperature and converts analog signals to digital form	Range: 0 – 1023 °C; Resolution: 0.25 °C; Accuracy: ±2 °C	Suitable for high temperature pyrolysis processes; provides fast response and stable output
Amplifier / Converter	MAX6675K Digital Thermocouple Amplifier	Performs signal conditioning and cold junction compensation	SPI Interface; 12-bit ADC; Low noise conversion	Ensures accurate digital output and reduces thermal drift
Microcontroller (Processing Unit)	Arduino Nano (ATmega328P)	Collects, processes, and transmits data to the IoT node	Clock: 16 MHz; Flash Memory: 32 KB; Operating Voltage: 5 V	Compact, low power, easy integration with sensors and

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

				communication modules
IoT Communication Module	ESP32 WiFi Microcontroller	Uploads processed data to ThingSpeak Cloud for remote visualization	Dual Core 32 bit Processor; Integrated WiFi and Bluetooth; Operating Voltage: 3.3 V	Provides stable wireless connectivity and IoT capability
Display Modules	LCD 2004 and OLED 1306	Display real time temperature data locally	LCD (20×4 characters); OLED (128×64 pixels); I ² C Interface	Allow clear visualization of multiple sensor readings
Power Supply	Lithium 18650 Battery with BMS and MP1584 Buck Converter	Provides regulated DC power for the system	Output Voltage: 5 V DC; Battery Capacity: 2200 mAh (each cell); Conversion Efficiency: 92 %	Portable, rechargeable, ensures stable voltage and safe operation

2.3 Software and Firmware Development

The software and firmware development of the IoT enabled real time temperature data logger were designed to coordinate sensing, processing, and communication functions for accurate data acquisition and remote visualization. Programming was carried out using the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE), employing C and C++ languages to develop distinct but complementary firmware for the Arduino Nano (ATmega328P) and the ESP32

microcontroller. The Arduino Nano was programmed to collect temperature readings from four thermocouple sensors through the MAX6675K amplifier modules via the Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) protocol. The firmware continuously samples data from each sensor channel, converts the raw readings into temperature values, and stores them in floating-point variables. These data are serialized into JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format for structured and efficient data exchange between the microcontrollers. The Arduino also controls

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

the LCD 2004 and OLED 1306 display modules through the I²C communication interface, updating real time temperature readings for onsite monitoring during reactor operation.

The ESP32 microcontroller functions as the IoT gateway that enables wireless communication between the laboratory setup and the ThingSpeak cloud platform. It receives the serialized temperature data from the Arduino Nano through a Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter (UART) interface, deserializes them, and uploads the processed readings to the cloud using the HTTP protocol and unique API keys for secure authentication. Once transmitted, the data are automatically

displayed on a web-based dashboard that allows remote monitoring of the temperature profile in real time. The firmware includes automatic WiFi reconnection and error handling routines to prevent data loss during network interruptions, ensuring consistent operation. The overall workflow of the firmware process is summarized in Figure 3, which illustrates the sequential flow from initialization and sensor reading to data processing, display update, JSON serialization, and cloud upload. This modular and open source approach enhances scalability, portability, and maintainability, making the system adaptable for future extensions to other IoT based thermal or industrial monitoring applications.

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

Figure 3: Flowchart of the IoT-enabled Temperature Data Logger

2.4 System Integration and Calibration

System integration involved the systematic connection and synchronization of all hardware modules to ensure coordinated operation between the sensing, control, display, and communication units of the data logger. The circuit configuration of the system, as shown in Figure 4, illustrates the interconnection between the four K type thermocouples, each interfaced with a MAX6675K amplifier module, and the

Arduino Nano microcontroller, which handles temperature data acquisition and processing. The Arduino communicates with the ESP32 microcontroller through UART serial communication, allowing wireless transmission of data to the ThingSpeak cloud platform for remote monitoring. The LCD 2004 and OLED 1306 modules were connected via the I²C interface for local display of temperature readings. The entire circuit is powered by a

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

lithium ion 18650 battery pack regulated by an MP1584 DC to DC converter to supply a stable 5 V DC to all modules, while a Battery

Management System (BMS) ensures safe operation during charging and discharging.

Figure 4: Circuit diagram of the IoT-enabled temperature data logger

The physical implementation of the circuit is presented in Figure 5, which shows the hardware assembly of the developed data logger. Each component was carefully mounted to minimize electromagnetic interference and ensure efficient wiring between the sensing, control, and display sections. The final assembly of the complete system, displayed in Figure 6, demonstrates the compact and portable configuration of the device, suitable for laboratory scale applications. Calibration of the system was conducted to

validate measurement accuracy and operational reliability. The calibration procedure involved comparing temperature readings from the data logger with those obtained from a standard laboratory thermometer under controlled thermal conditions. Differences observed were recorded and used to compute correction factors embedded in the firmware. The calibrated system exhibited a maximum deviation of ± 2 °C, confirming its accuracy and stability. Continuous operational tests further verified consistent performance, demonstrating that the integrated and calibrated system provides reliable real time

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

temperature monitoring for laboratory scale
pyrolysis reactor applications.

Figure 5: Hardware assembly of the IoT-enabled temperature data logger

Figure 6: Complete assembly of the IoT-enabled temperature data logger

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

2.5 Performance Evaluation Methodology

The performance evaluation of the developed IoT enabled real time temperature data logger was conducted to examine its operational efficiency and reliability under laboratory conditions. The test setup, illustrated in Figure 7, involved interfacing the data logger with a laboratory scale pyrolysis reactor to assess its ability to capture and record temperature variations during operation. Four K type thermocouple sensors were strategically positioned at key thermal zones, including the heater, reactor chamber, condenser outlet, and condenser inlet, to monitor temperature distribution within the

system. The data logger was powered by its integrated lithium-ion battery module and operated continuously for a one-hour duration, during which temperature readings from all sensing points were acquired in real time. The recorded data were displayed locally on the LCD and OLED screens and simultaneously transmitted to the ThingSpeak cloud platform for remote visualization and storage. This evaluation procedure was designed to verify the functional integrity, stability, and responsiveness of the system, thereby demonstrating its capability to perform accurate and consistent temperature monitoring for laboratory scale pyrolysis reactor applications

Figure 7: Experimental setup for evaluating the temperature data logger

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

The developed IoT enabled real time temperature data logger successfully recorded

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

temperature variations from the four sensing points of the laboratory scale pyrolysis reactor during the one-hour operation period. The temperature readings obtained from the heater, reactor chamber, condenser inlet, and condenser outlet are presented in Table 2. The results show

Table 2: Result of the experimentation

Time (min)	Heater (°C)	Reactor (°C)	Condenser Outlet (°C)	Condenser Inlet (°C)
0	35.50	31.50	27.25	26.75
10	277.00	89.25	27.50	27.50
20	342.25	120.50	27.75	27.75
30	429.00	224.25	28.25	28.25
40	537.00	289.25	28.75	28.07
50	611.50	320.25	29.25	28.75
60	695.50	350.00	30.00	29.75

The corresponding temperature trends are shown in Figures 8 and 9, illustrating the variations across the heating and condensation zones of the reactor. The heater and reactor exhibited consistent thermal responses as heat was applied, while the condenser sections

a steady temperature rise at the heater and reactor zones, indicating progressive heat transfer during the pyrolysis process, while the condenser inlet and outlet maintained relatively low and stable temperatures due to the cooling effect within the condensation section.

displayed minimal variation, confirming stable cooling performance. The data visualization on the ThingSpeak cloud platform, presented in Figure 10, further confirms successful real time acquisition and transmission of temperature readings throughout the experimental period.

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

Figure 8: Experimental results at the heater and reactor

Figure 9: Experimental results at the condenser inlet and outlet

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

Figure 10: Temperature chart of condenser inlet on ThingSpeak platform

3.2 Discussion

The experimental results shown in Figures 8 and 9 demonstrate that the developed IoT enabled real time temperature data logger effectively captured the thermal behavior of the laboratory scale pyrolysis reactor. The heater and reactor zones exhibited a steady temperature rise, with the heater reaching about 700 °C and the reactor approximately 350 °C after 60 minutes, indicating efficient heat transfer within the system. These temperature trends are consistent with expected pyrolysis conditions and align with recent findings reported by Aminu *et al.* (2023) and Zhao *et al.* (2022), who observed similar heating profiles in biomass pyrolysis at comparable scales. The condenser inlet and

outlet maintained low and stable temperatures of approximately 30 °C and 29 °C, respectively, reflecting the effectiveness of the cooling unit in facilitating vapor condensation. This observation agrees with studies by Soomro *et al.* (2022) and Odetoye *et al.* (2024), which emphasize that maintaining a narrow condenser temperature range is crucial for efficient bio oil recovery and minimizing secondary reactions. The distinct temperature gradients observed across the heating and cooling sections validate the data logger's ability to provide accurate and consistent thermal profiling, supporting effective process control and performance evaluation in laboratory pyrolysis systems.

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

The ThingSpeak temperature chart in Figure 10 further confirms the system's reliable IoT functionality and real time data transmission capability. Continuous data acquisition without signal interruption demonstrates the robustness of the ESP32 communication module and efficiency of the JSON based data protocol. The synchronization between local display readings and cloud visualization highlights the system's suitability for remote monitoring and data management. Overall, the developed data logger proved to be a reliable, low cost, and scalable instrument for continuous temperature measurement, offering valuable potential for wider applications in thermal system analysis, laboratory research, and industrial process monitoring.

4. CONCLUSION

This study successfully developed and evaluated an IoT enabled real time temperature data logger for laboratory scale pyrolysis reactor applications, integrating K type thermocouples, MAX6675K amplifier modules, an Arduino Nano for data acquisition, and an ESP32 microcontroller for wireless data transmission. The system demonstrated excellent operational stability and data reliability, effectively capturing temperature variations across the heater, reactor chamber, condenser inlet, and condenser outlet. The heater and reactor recorded peak values of 695.5 °C and 350 °C respectively within one hour

REFERENCES

Aboelela, D., Saleh, H., Attia, A. M., Elhenawy, Y., Majozi, T., and Bassyouni, M. (2023).

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

of operation, indicating efficient heat transfer and thermal response consistent with expected pyrolysis behavior, while the condenser sections maintained stable temperatures of approximately 30 °C and 29 °C, confirming the effective performance of the cooling unit. The consistent readings, local display functionality, and uninterrupted real time data flow to the ThingSpeak cloud platform validated the system's precision, responsiveness, and IoT capability for remote monitoring and visualization. The results establish the data logger as a dependable, low cost, and energy efficient solution for laboratory and pilot scale thermal process monitoring. Beyond pyrolysis applications, its robustness and IoT integration make it suitable for broader uses in smart farming, robotics, and industrial automation, particularly in resource constrained environments. Future improvements will focus on extending the system to multi parameter sensing, incorporating pressure and humidity measurement, and implementing automated control and mobile based visualization to enhance its adaptability for advanced thermal and industrial monitoring applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors appreciate the technical support received from the laboratories of Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa, Nigeria.

Recent advances in biomass pyrolysis processes for bioenergy production: optimization of operating conditions.

Sustainability, 15(14), 11238.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/su151411238>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1751851>

[2](#)

Abrar, M. D. and Patil, R. R. (2013). Multipoint Temperature Data Logger and Display on PC through Zigbee using PSoC. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, 2(9), 3382–3391.

Akinsade, A., Yaru, S. S., and Akinola, A. O. (2025). Development of an Auto-Logged Laboratory-Scale Pyrolysis Reactor. *OAUSTECH Journal of Engineering and Intelligent Technology*, 1(1), 128–137. <https://doi.org/10.36108/ojeit/5202.10.0141>

Bora, A. and Sarma, K. C. (2012). Design of a USB based Multichannel, Low-Cost Data Acquisition System using PIC Microcontroller. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 59(6), 0975–8887. <https://doi.org/10.5120/9550-4006>

Iyaomolere, B. A., Oluwasegun, O. O., Taiwo, D. E., and Oridupa, O. E. (2025). Development and Performance Evaluation of a Sustainable Bluetooth-Controlled Led Matrix Scoreboard for Real-Time Sports Applications. *OAUSTECH Journal of Engineering and Intelligent Technology*, 1(2), 182–191.

Mogaji, T. S., Akinsade, A., and Akintunde, M. A. (2019). Pyrolysis of Sugarcane Bagasse for Bio-oil Production. *Journal of Engineering and Engineering Technology, FUTAJEET*, 13(2), 150–157.

Obi, A. I., Iloeje, O. C., and Anyaoha, C. O. (2020). Design, Fabrication and Testing of Prototype Microcontroller Based Multipurpose Multichannel Electric Logger. In *Proceedings of the Second NIEEE Nsukka Chapter Conference on Sustainable Infrastructure Development in Developing Nations*, Nsukka, Nigeria, 26–29 February 2020; 1(2), 44–50.

Obi, A. I., Udosen, A. N., and Anyaoha, C. O. (2019). Design, Construction and Testing of Multipoint Humidity, Temperature Data Logger. In *Proceedings of the 1st International Multidisciplinary Conference on Technology*, Nsukka, Nigeria, December 2019; 1, 101–109.

Ojike, O., Mbajiorgu, C. C., Anoliefo, E., and Okonkwo, W. I. (2016). Design and Analysis of a Multipoint Temperature Data Logger. *Nigerian Journal of Technology (NIJOTECH)*, 35, 458–464. <https://doi.org/10.4314/njt.v35i2.30>

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**

- Osinowo, M., Willoughby, A., Dairo, O., Ewetumo, T., and Kolawole, L. (2022). Development of Ultra Low-Cost Data Acquisition System (DAS) for Developing Countries. *Trends in Sciences*, 19(13), 4639–4639.
<https://doi.org/10.48048/tis.2022.4639>
- Pedroza, M., Sousa, J., Vieira, G., and Bezerra, M. (2014). Characterization of the products from the pyrolysis of sewage sludge in 1 kg/h rotating cylinder reactor. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, 105, 108–115.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2013.10.09>
- Prima, E. C., Karim, S., Utari, S., Ramdani, R., Putri, E. R. R., and Darmawati, S. M. (2017). Heat transfer lab kit using temperature sensor based arduinoTM for educational purpose. *Procedia Engineering*, 170, 536–540.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.03.085>
- Sarma, P., Singh, H. K., and Bezboruah, T. (2018). A real-time data acquisition system for monitoring sensor data. *International Journal of Computer Science and Engineering*, 6(6), 539–542. Available online:
<http://www.ijcseonline.org/>
- Waghmare, M. B. and Chatur, P. N. (2012). Temperature and Humidity Analysis using Data Logger of Data Acquisition System: An Approach. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering*, 2(1), 102–106.
- Zhairy, A. E., Daoud, A. O., and Mohamed, A. G. (2025). Transforming facility management with BIM, IoT, and Digital Twin: a data-driven approach to air quality monitoring. *Architectural Engineering and Design Management*, 1–20.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17452007.2025.2543813>

***A. Akinsade, B. A. Iyaomolere, O. O. Oluwasegun, A. R. Lasisi**